

FAIR Data Implementation: Extending the portfolio of EOSC services with FAIR data repositories

SSHOC, Repositories, CoreTrustSeal & FAIR

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Repository & Preservation

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Realising the European Open Science Cloud 2020-11-17

Project:

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Type of action & funding:
Research and Innovation action
(INFRAEOSC-04-2018)

Partners: 44

(19 beneficiaries + 25 LTPs)

SSH ESFRI Landmarks and Projects
& international SSH data infrastructures

Project budget:

€ 14,455,594.08

Duration: 40 months

(January 2019 – 30 April 2022)

Project website:

www.SSHOC.eu

Objectives:

- creating the social sciences and humanities (**SSH**) part of European Open Science Cloud (**EOSC**)
- maximising **re-use** through **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles (standards, common catalogue, access control, semantic techniques, training)
- interconnecting existing and new infrastructures (clustered cloud infrastructure)
- establishing appropriate **governance model** for SSH-EOSC

FAIR

FAIR Data Into Reality

SSHOC Project

EOSC-Hub Project

EOSC Roadmap

SSHOC Work Packages

SSHOC Work Packages

WP8: Governance/ Sustainability/ Quality Assurance

- Governance model for the SSH part of the EOSC
- Stakeholders involvement and sustainability
- Data policies harmonization
- Aligning strategic activities and exploiting synergies
- Quality and ethical requirements for research data (including certification, training and support)
- Cross-disciplinary coordination and cooperation

WP8: Governance/ Sustainability/ Quality Assurance

Task 8.2 Trust & Quality Assurance

- CoreTrustSeal Certification
- Outsourcing & complex partnerships
- Common, standardised approaches provide for consistent EOSC data providers and data sources
- Appropriate technical and organisational measures in line with the GDPR

WP8: Governance/ Sustainability/ Quality Assurance

Task 8.2 Trust & Quality Assurance

- D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories (M12)
 - D8.2 created a certification plan for the SSHOC repositories, including an overview of the certification T9.2 status as well as the certification goal for each repository.
- D8.3 Report on TDR status and certification solutions for SSHOC repositories (M38)
 - D8.3 will evaluate repository services (OAIS Reference Model/Trustworthy Digital Repository terms) and define the criteria by which trusted services might be outsourced within the TDR model to support complex partnership models

CoreTrustSeal Process

HLH-CoreTrustSeal-Process_01_00.vsdX

CoreTrustSeal Process: with SSHOC Support

HLH-CoreTrustSeal-Process-SSHOC_00_03.vsdX

Trust Support: SSHOC, Beyond SSHOC & FAIR

- SSHOC

- Extension of the CESSDA Trust model
- Direct support to interested repositories (Confidential)
- Provision of wider supporting materials (Open)

- EOSC-Nordic

- Repository support with FAIR elements

- FAIRsFAIR

- CoreTrustSeal+FAIR and maturity

- +N

- Next?

CoreTrustSeal

Mandatory Responsibilities (OAIS)

HLH-OAIS-MandatoryResponsibilities_00_02.vsdX

Storage>Curation>Preservation>

Organisation

Objects

Technology & Security

CoreTrustSeal

HLH-CoreTrustSeal-4FAIR_02_00_vsd_x

EOSC FAIR
Executive Board Working Group

- Certification
- Metrics

F.A.I.R Data

FAIR Principles

FAIR Principles, Indicators, Metrics and Tests

HLH-FAIR-AcronymPrinciplesIndicatorsMetricsTests_02_00.vsdX

Repositories and Objects

Repository ObjectMetadata A_00_01.vsd

Objects (Data & Metadata) vs Repositories (Process & Business Information)

Assessment & Evaluation

HLH-GenericEvaluationReferenceModel-A-_v03_00.vsdX

CoreTrustSeal+FAIR: Repositories as Context for Objects

F

R13

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.
- F2. data are described with rich metadata.
- F3. metadata specify the data identifier.
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

R13. Data discovery and identification

A

R15

R16

R10

- A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
- A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable (vs context)
- A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
- A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

R15. Technical infrastructure

R16. Security

R10. Preservation plan

I

R15

R11

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles (vs context)
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

R15. Technical infrastructure (Business Information? Object Model?)

R11. Data quality

R

R11

R2

R7

R15

- R1. meta(data) have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
- R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
- R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance.
- R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards (vs Context)

R11. Data quality

R2. Licenses

R7. Data integrity and authenticity

R15. Technical infrastructure

HLH-CoreTrustSeal-FAIR-Map_02_00.vsd

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): Vision

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Beyond the Current CoreTrustSeal

References

- **SSHOC**
 - SSHOC D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3725868>
- **EOSC-Nordic**
 - Certification support seminar on FAIR data <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/certification-support-seminar-on-fair-data/>
- **CESSDA**
 - CESSDA Working Groups <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Working-Groups>
 - Overview of Support Approaches <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4020399>
- **CoreTrustSeal**
 - Extended Guidance <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632533>
 - Glossary <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3632563>
 - Conversational CoreTrustSeal <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4033966> (Unofficial)
- **FAIRsFAIR**
 - M4.2 Draft Maturity Model Based on Extensions and-or Additions to CoreTrustSeal Requirements <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4003598>
 - M4.5 Evaluation of Procedures and Processes of Certification Mechanisms Provided <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3738965>
 - FAIR Ecosystem Components: Vision <https://zenodo.org/record/3565428#.X7GPLGj7SUK>

Thank you for your attention!

www.sshoc.eu

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